

STUDIES ON VITAMIN-A IN SOLUTION. PART I. STABILITY

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Stability of vitamin-A in different diluents has been studied both with and without the addition of antioxidants. Unsaturation in diluent is not the sole cause of deterioration of vitamin-A molecule in solution. The antioxidant is found to exert a better effect in protecting the vitamin-A molecule when the system contains an ester (saturated or unsaturated) or a glyceride. In such case no difference has been noticed between the two antioxidants, methylhydroquinone or propyl gallate. Details of vitamin-A assay have also been described.

From economic and commercial points of view the preparation of vitamin-A in suitable vegetable oil is now being advocated. The oil may, however, develop rancidity due to the formation of peroxides, and these peroxides would destroy the vitamin potency. This oxidation may be controlled to a considerable extent by the incorporation of some suitable antioxidant (Whipple, *Oil & Soap*, 1936, 18, 231; Lowen *et al.*, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1937, 29, 151; Basu, *Ann. Biochem. Exp. Med.*, 1941, 1, 165). The nature of the solvent would considerably play a role on the stability of the vitamin (cf. Basu, *loc. cit.*). Sesame oil has been found by Sen Gupta (this *Journal*, 1946, 23, 233) to destroy the vitamin-A potency of shark liver oil (cf. also Basu and Ray, *Science & Culture*, 1947, 18, 73). The stability of vitamin-A in different solvents and that again in presence of different antioxidants in varying concentrations have been studied and described in the present paper. The mode of oxidation has been discussed in Part II of this paper.

The vitamin-A in the preparation was estimated by means of an Adam-Hilger's vitameter-A in the oil or ester solution after saponification, when the concentration was low (below 10,000 I.U. per g.) and when present in concentrated form or in liquid paraffin, directly by dissolving in alcohol or in a mixture of ether and alcohol respectively. Details of the methods of estimation are recorded in the experimental part.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials.—The vitamin used was a vitamin-A concentrate made by saponification containing 0.2 million I.U. per g.

The refined and deodorised arachis oil, as obtained from the market, was further dried by shaking with freshly heated and cooled anhydrous sodium sulphate and kept in a glass stoppered bottle overnight, and filtered under suction through a dry Buchner. Liquid paraffin of B. P. specification was similarly dried and purified. Ethyl oleate and ethyl stearate were prepared in the laboratory and the fractions distilling between 196° and 206° under 7-8 mm. pressure in each case were collected and stored in glass stoppered bottles. Glyceryl monolaurate was purchased from the market (Glyco Products Co U.S.A.). The specification and the characteristic of the diluents are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Characteristics of solvents.

Characteristics.	Arachis oil.	Ethyl oleate.	Ethyl stearate.	Glyceryl monolaurate & liquid paraffin (1:1).
Acid value	Nil	Nil	0.08	5.02
Sap. value	185	—	180.0	105.0
Iodine value	92.8	80.7	1.05	4.0
Rancidity (U. S. P. xiii)	Nil	—	—	—
Unsaponifiable matter	0.48%	Nil	—	—
Refractive index	1.4634/40°	1.4497/25°	—	1.4699/25°
Specific gravity	0.9144/25°	0.8682/25°	—	0.9326/25°
Peroxide value	—	Passes B P. test	Nil	Nil

The antioxidants used were methylhydroquinone (m.p. 54-56°) and *n*-propyl gallate (m.p. 146-48°) prepared in the laboratory. The concentrations used were 0.02% and 0.05% in the former case and 0.02, 0.05 and 0.1% in the latter.

Aeration.—The vitamin-A concentrate was carefully weighed into a special container and suitably diluted with different solvents. The different solutions were then transferred to amber colored resistant glass bottles fitted with perforated corks that allowed introduction of glass tubings for aeration. Antioxidants were directly weighed into the aeration bottles; in case of liquid paraffin, propyl gallate had to be dissolved by addition of a few drops of peroxide-free ether. Usually 25 c.c. of the solutions were used for each experiment. The whole was set up in diffused light and air, purified and dried by passing through sulphuric acid and soda lime tower, was passed (4 c.c. per second) through the systems kept at the room temperature (28°-29°) in all cases except the preparation made with glyceryl monolaurate *cum* liquid paraffin (1:1) where the system was kept in a thermostat adjusted to 33° in order to maintain the preparation in the liquid state.

Estimation of Vitamin-A.—Before aeration the vitamin potency was estimated in each case, and then during aeration samples were taken out from the system at intervals for determination of vitamin-A. The whole procedure is described below.

Apparatus and Reagents.—Care was taken that the appliances used were absolutely free from any metallic or other impurities and were specially reserved for this purpose. The stop-cocks of the separating funnel were not lubricated with ordinary grease or any ether-soluble lubricant. A starch-glycerin lubricant, as described by Herrington and Starr (*Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1942, 14, 62) was found suitable.

The sample (2g approx.) was saponified for 15-20 minutes. The unsaponifiable matter was extracted in the usual way with peroxide-free ether and the ether extract was dried in nitrogen atmosphere. The dried extract was immediately taken up in aldehyde-free alcohol (12 c.c.) in case of pure oil or ester and peroxide-free, dried ether (12 c.c.) in case where it was mixed up with liquid paraffin. The volume was made up to 25 c.c. in each case with absolute and aldehyde-free alcohol. In most cases this solution had to be diluted further to have the vitameter A reading within the range of 6 to 9.

In case of pure liquid paraffin system, 0.2 to 0.5 g. of the sample was directly weighed

into a 25 c.c. volumetric flask, dissolved in ether and alcohol (1:1) mixture, diluted if necessary and the vitameter A reading was taken as usual.

The potency of the vitamin-A (I.U. per g.) as recorded in various tables below was found out from the formula $X \times 1600/Y$, where X = vitameter A reading and Y = percentage strength of the sample taken in the vitameter cell.

Liquid paraffin being insoluble in alcohol, the samples from this system were taken in ether-alcohol mixture and in order to find out that this change of solvent would not affect the vitameter A reading, control experiments were carried out with (1) pure alcohol, (2) pure ether, (3) mixture of alcohol and ether (1:1) and (4) a solution containing 0.2 g. of liquid paraffin per 25 c.c. of a similar mixture of alcohol and ether. From the result in Table X it would be evident that the above change in the nature of the solvent did not affect the vitameter reading.

TABLE II

Arachis oil.

Aerated for.	Without antioxidant		With 0.05% propyl gallate	
	Vitamin-A (I. U./g.)	% Loss of vitamin-A,	Vitamin-A (I U./g)	% Loss of vitamin-A.
0	728	0	728	0
52 hrs.	303	58.8	—	—
66	—	—	574	21.1
100	195	73.2	—	—
128	—	—	534	26.6
149	173	76.2	—	—
177	—	—	500	31.3

TABLE III

Ethyl oleate.

Aerated for.	Without antioxidant		With 0.05% propyl gallate	
	Vitamin-A (I U./g.)	% Loss of vitamin-A.	Vitamin-A (I. U./g).	% Loss of vitamin-A.
0	740	0	740	0
52 hrs.	300	59.5	—	—
66	—	—	591	20.1
94	196	73.5	—	—
100	—	—	530	28.4
149	190	74.3	—	—
160	—	—	510	31.1

TABLE IV

Ethyl stearate.

Aerated for.	Without antioxidant		With 0.05% propyl gallate	
	Vitamin-A (I. U./g.).	% Loss of Vitamin-A.	Vitamin-A (I. U./g.).	% Loss of vitamin-A.
0	700	0	700	0
59 hrs.	480	31.4	—	—
73	—	—	661	5.6
100	408	41.7	—	—
135	—	—	555	20.7
156	372	46.9	—	—
184	—	—	482	31.1

TABLE V

Liquid paraffin.

Aerated for.	Without antioxidant		With 0.05% propyl gallate	
	Vitamin-A (I. U./g.).	% Loss of Vitamin-A.	Vitamin-A (I. U./g.).	% Loss of vitamin-A
0	1100	0	1100	0
87 hrs.	512	53.5	658	40.2
142	305	72.3	620	43.7
191	222	79.8	610	44.6

TABLE VI

Liquid paraffin cum ethyl oleate (1 : 1).

Aerated for.	Without antioxidant		With 0.05% propyl gallate	
	Vitamin-A (I. U./g.).	% Loss of vitamin-A.	Vitamin-A (I. U./g.).	% Loss of vitamin-A.
0	700	0	700	0
70 hrs.	203	71	—	—
77	—	—	568	18.9
155	150	78.6	—	—
162	—	—	475	32.1
192	125	82.1	450	35.7

TABLE VII

Liquid paraffin cum ethyl stearate (1 : 1).

Aerated for.	Without antioxidant		With 0.05% propyl gallate	
	Vitamin-A (I. U./g.).	% Loss of vitamin-A.	Vitamin-A (I. U./g.).	% Loss of vitamin-A.
0	650	0	650	0
42 hrs.	600	7.7	—	—
63	—	—	627	3.5
141	349	46.3	—	—
148	—	—	545	16.2
177	254	60.9	—	—
185	—	—	489	24.8

TABLE VIII

Liquid paraffin cum glyceryl monolaurate (1 : 1).

Aerated for	Without antioxidant		With 0.05% Propyl gallate	
	Vitamin-A (I. U./g.).	% Loss of vitamin-A.	Vitamin-A (I. U./g.).	% Loss of vitamin-A.
0	750	0	750	0
59 hrs.	584	22.1	—	—
66	—	—	712	5.1
100	360	52.0	—	—
108	—	—	672	10.4
170	235	68.7	—	—
177	—	—	648	13.6
230	213	73.6	—	—
238	—	—	617	17.7

TABLE IX

Arachis oil : Variation of proportions and nature of antioxidant.

Aerated for.	0.02% Monomethyl hydroquinone.		0.05% Monomethyl hydroquinone.		0.02% Propyl gallate		0.05% Propyl gallate.		0.1% Propyl gallate	
	Vitamin-A (I. U./g.).	% Loss of vitamin-A.	Vitamin-A (I. U./g.).	% Loss of vitamin-A.	Vitamin-A (I. U./g.).	% Loss of vitamin-A.	Vitamin-A (I. U./g.).	% Loss of vitamin-A.	Vitamin-A (I. U./g.).	% Loss of vitamin-A.
0	900	0	900	0	900	0	900	0	900	0
42 hrs.	760	15.6	754	16.2	732	18.7	780	13.3	765	15.0
90	530	42.2	512	43.1	503	44.1	515	42.8	525	41.7
150	468	48.0	475	47.3	472	47.6	485	46.1	490	45.6

TABLE X

Effect of solvent in vitameter reading.

No.	Description	Vitameter reading.
1	Cell with pure alcohol	0.1
2	" " " ether	0.1
3	" " " alcohol-ether (1 : 1)	0.1
4	" " " containing 0.2 g. liquid paraffin	0.1

DISCUSSION

From the Tables II and III it would be noticed that the rate of loss of potency of vitamin-A on aeration, both in presence and in absence of antioxidant, is almost the same in case of a natural glyceride (arachis oil) or an artificial ester made from an unsaturated acid (ethyl oleate). In case of an ester from a saturated fatty acid (ethyl stearate), the loss in absence of an antioxidant is somewhat less (Table IV) showing thereby that the unsaturation of the diluent plays a part in the deterioration of vitamin-A in absence of antioxidant. When the antioxidant is present, the rate is, however, comparable to those of the former two cases. From the data in Table V it appears that the above loss in potency is not due to the onset of oxidation in the fat molecule alone, since in the case of liquid paraffin, a saturated system, the vitamin undergoes more deterioration. That an ester molecule in presence of an antioxidant seems to play a role in inhibiting the oxidation is again evident from the results of experiments as carried out with the systems liquid paraffin containing ethyl stearate (Table VII), glyceryl monolaurate (Table VIII) and ethyl oleate (Table VI). From Table V, it may be noticed that the antioxidant also inhibits the oxidation of the vitamin molecule even when present in liquid paraffin system (cf. Basu and Bhattacharya, *Science & Culture*, 1949, 14, 481).

The observations, as recorded in Table IX, indicate that in the systems studied methylhydroquinone behaves in the same way as propyl gallate and there is no significant difference in the antioxidenic function when the concentration is changed from 0.02 to 0.1%. The studies made with the liquid paraffin system (Table V) tend to show that the deterioration of vitamin-A is due to the changes in the vitamin-A molecule, and this deterioration is inhibited to a considerable extent when an ester molecule with an antioxidant is present. It is apparent therefore that the unsaturation in the diluent in any vitamin-A preparation, as discussed previously by Basu (cf. *Ann. Biochem. Exp. Med.*, 1941, 1, 165), is not the only cause of deterioration of the vitamin. On the contrary, vitamin-A in presence of an antioxidant is being found to be more stable on aeration in an unsaturated glyceride or an ester system than in a liquid paraffin system. Further, from the fact that vitamin-A potency is maintained to the same degree in the saturated or unsaturated glyceride or ester system in presence of an antioxidant, the question arises whether the glyceride (natural or artificial) as well as the ester molecule plays a role in helping the antioxidant in inhibiting the onset of oxidation in the vitamin-A molecule. Further work is in progress.